
FACTORS INFLUENCING MOTIVATION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN
FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract. Learning a language is not just school subject or basic requirement – it is a very important and valuable skill in today’s world. It helps to people communicate and understand each other. This is important in the modern world, especially for school students. For students to learn a language willingly, they need motivation. It is the secondary school students who struggle the most in this regard – their motivation is often lower than that of younger or older students.

This article focuses on the motivation of middle school students, we will examine their psychological and pedagogical characteristics as well as their motivation. We will analyze 2 main factors influencing motivation, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Also, explore how these students think, learn, evaluate themselves, and their relationship with classmates, parents, teachers. The goal of this study is to increase secondary school students’ interest in lesson, motivation to learn. This article examines the factors that influence students’ learning speed – why some learn quickly while others learn slowly or fail to learn at all. We will highlight the use of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in teaching methods.

In 21st century, of rapidly developing technologies and digital tools, maintaining students’ motivation and interest in lessons have become increasingly challenging.

Keywords: motivation, foreign language learning, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, secondary school students.

Ключевые слова: мотивация, изучение иностранного языка, внутренняя мотивация, внешняя мотивация, учащиеся средней школы.

Introduction

Learning languages is not just a school lesson. It is also very important and useful for communication, helping people talk to and understand each other. However, many modern children and students currently have very low motivation to study a language. Due to this lack of motivation, their learning process is slow and difficult. Therefore, it is very important for the teacher to support and assist students, to maintain their motivation and help improve their interest in the language.

Motivation is a basic factor in learning a foreign language, especially for secondary school students. At this stage of development learners show strong psychological characteristics, including emotional sensitivity and fluctuation in attention and focus. Social environment also has a significant influence, which can negatively affect their development and language learning.

Motivation can be divided into two types: intrinsic, which comes from personal interest and enjoyment, and extrinsic, which comes from social expectations. Research have shown that students with strong intrinsic motivation usually perform well in language learning, actively participate in class and complete their work on time. On the other hand, students with low motivation tend to learn slowly, show low interest and achieve poor results in developing their language skills.

Teenagers’ motivation is also influenced by their thinking skills, self-confidence and interactions with others. Nowadays, secondary school students are capable of thinking independently, making their own decisions and setting personal goals and minds in evaluating

their knowledge. These skills and qualities help to increase their motivation. Additionally, in boosting motivation, the guidance and support provided by the teacher play a big role (Filgona et al., 2020). Motivation also depends on the student’s attitude. If they see the benefits of learning and feel that the classroom is safe and friendly, they will find lessons more meaningful. When students’ emotional and social needs are met and they fell competent and understand the importance of their goals, more likely to stay motivated. Clear goals and positive feedback also encourage them to work harder and be better prepared for lessons.

Teachers can help students by creating lessons that are challenging but achievable. Learners can have choices in what they do, work in teams, participate in group discussions, assess their classmates’ work and peer correction. These activities can increase motivation by addressing students’ needs and giving them a sense of responsibility and involvement (Maulida, 2019).

Motivation strongly affects the development of the four main language skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing (Yulfi, & Aalayina, 2021). Motivated students actively look for ways to practice and correct their mistakes independently. They take responsibility for their own learning, find opportunities to improve and try to understand their errors in order to do better next time. Such students are more engaged, persistent and willing to put in extra effort to achieve their goals.

The main aim of this work is to comprehensively study the key factors that influence the motivation of middle school students in learning a foreign language. It also discusses how teachers can help students, understand their needs and improve their learning and teaching process. The paper will include the following sections: methods, result and discussion.

Methods

Every year, more and more people start learning new languages. This shows that language learning is becoming more and more important. Many people want to learn more than one language, of course, they choose English (Amoah & Yeboah, 2021). According to research, about 350 million people speak English as their first native language, and around 430 million people use it as a second learned language (Niyozova, 2020). This demonstrate that people all over the world can communicate in English. Today, it is considered a global and highly promising language. Therefore, English can become a main, key language in education, on the internet and for international purposes.

This study focused on secondary school students’ motivation, interest in lessons and their willingness to learn English as a second language. We used a mixed-methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative approaches to get a complete research.

The study was conducted with students from 5-6, but the main focus on 7th grade students. Using this mixed approach we not only measured students’ knowledge and motivation with numbers but also collected their opinions and experiences. They were divided into 2 groups: experimental group, which used the new motivation-focused method and the control group which continued learning using the traditional approach. All students has been learning English for about 5 years. Also, we monitored the students’ intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. The survey was conducted using L. V. Zharov’s method. It was in 3 stages:

1 - figure

Before the experiment:	During the experiment:	After the experiment:
Students took a test and motivation survey to measure their starting level.	1. The experimental group used a new method to increase motivation. 2. The control group continued with the regular program.	The test and survey were repeated to compare the results between the 2 groups. Then used the interview method.

Results

According to the result of the study, no significant difference was observed between the experimental group and the control group. The levels of motivation and learning outcomes in both groups remained largely similar, and noticeable changes were not detected. At the beginning, the motivation levels of both groups were almost the same. Experimental group – 62%, control group – 60%.

During the experiment, the experimental group began to show growth in both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. The students became more active, attended classes regularly and participated more during lessons. As they learned about the benefits and future opportunities associated with knowing English, their intrinsic motivation increased even further. They started learning with genuine interest and personal desire. In addition, when they received praise and warm, encouraging feedback, their engagement and motivation continued to rise.

Meanwhile, the control group remained at the same level. They did not receive additional support, encouragement or motivation feedback, therefore their learning behavior did not show noticeable changes. Experimental group – 81%, control group – 64%.

According to the final result, the experimental group demonstrated a clear increase in overall motivation compared to the control group. Which shows, experimental group – 19% growth, control group – 4%.

Discussion

The results show that motivation is one of the most important factors in learning a foreign language. Students with very high intrinsic motivation enjoy learning and are genuinely interested in the language (Lee & Lee, 2021). They attend classes regularly, practice more and usually demonstrate better results. On the other hand, students with lower motivation show little interest in learning. Their language skills do not fully develop and tend to make slower progress. These findings confirm that the level of motivation strongly influences how successfully a student learns a foreign language.

There are certain factors that influence the motivation of secondary school students. Their thinking skills, self-confidence, and social relationships can either increase or decrease their motivations to learn (Zhang et al., 2022). At this age, students begin to take an interest in and understand their personal goals, but they are also strongly influenced by the opinions of those around them. Support from teachers, parents, classmates can increase their motivation, while negative feedback or other unfavorable behaviors can, on the contrary, reduce their motivation.

Teachers play a very important role because they are one of the main people who guide students in learning a language. They can create a friendly, motivating classroom environment, plan lessons in an interesting and engaging way. This includes balancing independent work with group activities to keep students actively involved (Seven, 2020). For example, group projects, collaborative tasks, and interactive activities help students stay engaged (Zhang et al., 2020). Most importantly, teachers provide emotional support and positive feedback, which inspires and encourages students to stay motivated.

Using both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation is also effective. Intrinsic motivation helps students develop an enjoy for the learning, while extrinsic motivation can provide additional encouragement, especially when intrinsic motivation decreases (Olivier et al., 2020).

Conclusion

Motivation – factor that plays a significant role, especially for secondary school learners. Because they generally have lower motivation compared to younger or older students. It is influenced by their personal cognitive skills, self-esteem, relationships with others and classroom environment.

Both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation affect them, as these can have both positive and negative impact. Students with high intrinsic motivation participate in lessons actively, demonstrate better interest in language learning compared to students with low motivation. They often do not fully understand what is happening in class and do not practice enough. This was

confirmed by the experiments conducted during the study. The motivation of the experimental group increased by 19%, while the control group showed only a 4%.

At this age, it is very important for learners to take positive motivation from the people around them. They need recognition and approval from adults or peers. Therefore, it is important for middle school teachers, to provide the right positive motivation. They should always praise learners for their strengths and continuously encourage them by giving constructive and supportive feedback.

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